

QUIZ**LAST NAME: NYARWATI****FIRST NAME: JACOB****PROGRAM CODE: MDIA****COURSE CODE : ACA-401****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: Dr. Gulma****In this Response Paper 2:**

I applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

I used Turabian (Bibliography)

I used Zotero to insert references

I did use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

Finally, I also used the MSWord 2016 on Windows 8 software

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. **The following statements are TRUE about a good academic essay except?**

- It should have a thesis statement (answer to the question) and an argument.
- An academic essay should have supporting information, including hearsay evidence.¹**
- It should try to present or discuss something: to develop a thesis via a set of closely related points by reasoning and evidence.
- An academic essay should include relevant examples, supporting evidence and information from academic texts or credible sources.

2. **Citation of the author when writing an academic paper is one way of avoiding Plagiarism. The following statements about Plagiarism are TRUE except?**

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. 2nd ed. (Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2019), 1.

- Plagiarism is wrong and unethical.
 - It is not fair to take someone's work and not give them credit.
 - Paraphrasing someone else's ideas, and then citing the source of ideas.²**
 - It is a serious academic offense that can have serious consequences.
3. **Which of the following Latin expression means *female form of ibid*?**
- et alii*.
 - in situ*.
 - eadem*.³**
 - id est*.
4. **These different kinds of thinking are often divided into six levels. Which of the following is the most advanced level?**
- Analyzing.
 - Understanding.
 - Synthesizing.
 - Evaluating.⁴**
5. **Which of the following journal citations in a reference list is correct according to the author-date style in the Turabian manual?**

² Ibid., 4-12.

³ Ibid., 56.

⁴ Patrick Sebranek, Dave Kemper, and Verne Meyer, *Write Source 2000: A Guide to Writing, Thinking and Learning*, 4th ed. (Wilmington, MA: Great Source Education Group, 1999), 283.

- Kiser, L. J. (2011). *Silencing the Lambs: Economics, Ethics, and Animal Life in Medieval Franciscan Hagiography*. *Modern Philology* 108, no. 3: 323–42. Accessed September 18, 2011. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1086/658052>.
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6. **Per the Turabian manual,⁶ what are the two common scholarly citation styles? Please select the most accurate styles of citation forms.**
- Parenthetical style.
- Reference style.
- Notes-bibliography style.**
- Author-date style.**

⁵ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Eighth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, ed. Wayne C. Booth et al., 8th edition (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013), 130.

⁶ *Ibid.*, 87.

7. **For researchers, they may use different levels of sources, which of the following level of source is NOT mentioned in the Turabian manual?⁷**
- Quaternary Sources.**
 - Secondary Sources.
 - Primary Sources.
 - Tertiary Sources.
8. **Which of the following normally will NOT be considered as raw data when reporting research results?**
- Lists of observations.
 - A graph of data in a published journal.⁸**
 - Values documented on a laboratory notebook.
 - Medical chart records in a clinic.
9. **Which of the following abbreviations or contractions is accepted in the style guide by the University of Oxford?**
- A.M.
 - Dr.
 - DPhil.⁹**
 - Ph.D.
10. **The following statements are true about the English style guide handbook, Except?**

⁷ Kate L. Turabian, 24.

⁸ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401 Coursepack: Period 4*. 2nd ed. (Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2020), 10-11.

⁹ *Ibid.*, 75.

- The English style guide is intended primarily for only English-native speakers.¹⁰**
- The English style guide is intended primarily for English-language authors and translators.
- The rules, reminders and handy references of the English style guide aim to serve a wider readership as well.
- The English style guide also refers to recommended in-house usage, and not to literary style.

¹⁰ European Commission, *English Style Guide*. 7th ed. (European Commission, 2013), 1.

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.